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Graduates in the Italian Regions

They decreased between 2018 and 2022 by an amount equal to -0.7%

Istat calculates the percentage of graduates and holders of other tertiary qualifications in the Italian regions. The variable consists of the percentage of people aged 30-34 who have obtained a degree or tertiary qualification out of the total number of people aged 30-34.

Ranking of the Italian regions by value of graduates and other tertiary qualifications in 2022. Lazio is in first place by value of people in possession of a degree or other tertiary education qualifications in 2022 with an amount equal to 35.90, followed by 'Emilia Romagna with a value of 33.20, and from Molise with a value of 32.90. In the middle of the table are Trentino Alto Adige with a value of 28.80, followed by Marche with a value of 28.50 and Veneto with a value of 27.60. Sardinia closes the ranking with a value of 22.10, followed by Puglia with a value of 19.60 and Sicily with an amount of 17.80.

Ranking of the Italian regions by change in the value of graduates and other tertiary qualifications between 2018 and 2022. Molise is in first place for the value of the growth of graduates and holders of tertiary education qualifications with a value of 31.6% going from an amount of 25.00 to 32.9, followed by Calabria with an amount of +15.76%, and Abruzzo with a value of +15.68%. In the middle of the table are Sardinia with an amount of +2.79%, followed by Tuscany with a value of -0.68%, and Emilia Romagna with a value of -4.32%. Friuli Venezia Giulia closes the ranking with a value of -15.12%, followed by Piedmont with a value of -16.07% and Liguria with an amount of -16.28%.

Italian Macro-Regions. The value of graduates in Central Italy grew in the period between 2018 and 2022, going from a value of 30.2 to a value of 32.7 or a variation equal to an amount of 8.28% equal to an amount of 2.5 units. The value of graduates in Southern Italy grew between 2018 and 2022 by a value equal to 7.51% or by an amount equal to 1.6 units, going from 21.3 to a value of 22.9. Graduates in the South grew from a value of 21.2 in 2018 to a value of 21.6 in 2022 or by an amount of 0.4 units equal to 1.89%. The number of graduates in the North-West decreased from an amount of 32.2 units to a value of 29.3 units or equal to an amount of -9.01% equal to an amount of 2.9 units. The number of graduates in the Northern regions decreased from an amount of 32.7 units to a value of 29.6 units or equal to a reduction of -3.1 units equal to an amount of -9.48%. The number of graduates in the North East between 2018 and 2022 went from an amount of 33.3 units up to a value of 30.00 units or equal to an amount of -3.3 units equal to an amount of -9, 91%. The number of graduates in the Islands decreased from an amount of 20.9 units to a value of 18.8 units equal to a value of -2.1 units equal to an amount of -10.05%.

Clustering with k-Means algorithm optimized with the Silhouette coefficient. A clustering with k-Means algorithm optimized with the Silhouette coefficient is presented below. Two clusters are identified:

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- Cluster 1: Trentino Alto Adige, Veneto, Lombardy, Lazio, Marche, Tuscany, Emilia Romagna, Friuli Venezia Giulia, Umbria, Piedmont, Liguria, Valle d'Aosta, Molise, Abruzzo, Basilicata;
- Cluster 2: Puglia, Campania, Calabria, Sicily, Sardinia.

The results show a dominance of the regions of cluster 1 compared to the regions of cluster 2. There is therefore a dominance of the regions of the Centre-North compared to the regions of the South. The only three regions of the South that have high levels in terms of graduates and holders of tertiary education qualifications are Molise, Abruzzo and Basilicata.

Conclusions. If we consider the average value of the number of graduates and holders of tertiary education qualifications in the Italian regions we can note a reduction from an amount of 27.53 units up to a value of 27.32 units or a reduction equal to an amount of -0.21 units equals to a value of -0.76%. In particular, the average value of graduates and people who have acquired a tertiary education qualification in the Italian regions grew from an amount of 27.53 in 2018 to a value of 28.01 units in 2020. Between 2020 and 2021 the value of graduates decreased from an amount of 28.01 units to a value of 27.04 units. Between 2021 and 2022 the value of graduates grew to a value of 27.32 on average for the Italian regions. Covid-19 has therefore had an impact on reducing the number of graduates in the Italian regions with an average reduction of -3.46%. There are some regions in which the value of graduates has grown and these regions are Molise with +19.06%, Calabria with +5.88%, Tuscany with +4.32%, Emilia Romagna with +2.75%, Veneto with +2.33%. However, there are many regions which between 2020 and 2021 saw a reduction in the number of graduates, namely: Umbria with -0.29%, Puglia with -3.05%, Sicily with -3.78%, Trentino Alto Adige with -3.95%, Basilicata with -4.26%, Liguria with -4.38%, Valle d'Aosta with -4.48%, Lombardy with -4.86%, Piedmont with -5.19%, Marche with -8.25%, Lazio with -11.14%, Abruzzo with -11.73%, Sardinia with -16.15%, Friuli Venezia Giulia with -16.67%. The following propositions therefore derive: there is a gap between Central-Northern and Southern Italy in terms of number of graduates; the number of graduates decreased between 2020 and 2021 during Covid-19; Central Italy leads the ranking of Italian macro-regions in terms of graduates.

Declarations

Data Availability Statement. The data presented in this study are available on request from the corresponding author.

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Declaration of Competing Interest. The author declares that there is no conflict of interests regarding the publication of this manuscript. In addition, the ethical issues, including plagiarism, informed consent, misconduct, data fabrication and/or falsification, double publication.

Software. The authors have used the following software: Gretl for the econometric models, Orange for clusterization and network analysis, and KNIME for machine learning and predictions. They are all free version without licenses.

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Appendix

Regioni Italiane per Laureati e Persone con Tertiary Education					
Regioni	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022
<i>Piemonte</i>	★ 30,50	★ 27,50	★ 28,90	★ 27,40	★ 25,60
<i>Valle d'Aosta</i>	★ 27,40	★ 27,70	★ 29,00	★ 27,70	★ 30,60
<i>Liguria</i>	★ 30,10	★ 30,00	★ 27,40	★ 26,20	★ 25,20
<i>Lombardia</i>	★ 33,20	★ 33,10	★ 32,90	★ 31,30	★ 31,30
<i>Trentino-Alto Adige</i>	★ 32,80	★ 31,10	★ 30,40	★ 29,20	★ 28,80
<i>Veneto</i>	★ 31,90	★ 29,50	★ 30,10	★ 30,80	★ 27,60
<i>Friuli-Venezia Giulia</i>	★ 34,40	★ 33,10	★ 31,20	★ 26,00	★ 29,20
<i>Emilia-Romagna</i>	★ 34,70	★ 34,30	★ 32,70	★ 33,60	★ 33,20
<i>Toscana</i>	★ 29,60	★ 29,30	★ 27,80	★ 29,00	★ 29,40
<i>Umbria</i>	★ 27,90	★ 29,10	★ 34,00	★ 33,90	★ 30,80
<i>Marche</i>	★ 27,70	★ 29,20	★ 31,50	★ 28,90	★ 28,50
<i>Lazio</i>	★ 31,40	★ 33,60	★ 34,10	★ 30,30	★ 35,90
<i>Abruzzo</i>	★ 23,60	★ 27,10	★ 30,70	★ 27,10	★ 27,30
<i>Molise</i>	★ 25,00	★ 28,80	★ 27,80	★ 33,10	★ 32,90
<i>Campania</i>	★ 20,40	★ 21,10	★ 21,20	★ 21,20	★ 23,40
<i>Puglia</i>	★ 21,70	★ 20,10	★ 19,70	★ 19,10	★ 19,60
<i>Basilicata</i>	★ 25,70	★ 27,70	★ 25,80	★ 24,70	★ 23,60
<i>Calabria</i>	★ 20,30	★ 20,00	★ 20,40	★ 21,60	★ 23,50
<i>Sicilia</i>	★ 20,70	★ 20,30	★ 18,50	★ 17,80	★ 17,80
<i>Sardegna</i>	★ 21,50	★ 21,80	★ 26,00	★ 21,80	★ 22,10

Laureati Nelle Macro-Regioni Italiane. Istat-BES

Macro-Regioni	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022
<i>Nord</i>	★ 32,70	★ 31,60	★ 31,30	★ 30,40	★ 29,60
<i>Nord-ovest</i>	★ 32,20	★ 31,40	★ 31,40	★ 29,80	★ 29,30
<i>Nord-est</i>	★ 33,30	★ 31,90	★ 31,30	★ 31,30	★ 30,00
<i>Centro</i>	★ 30,20	★ 31,50	★ 31,90	★ 30,00	★ 32,70
<i>Mezzogiorno</i>	★ 21,20	★ 21,30	★ 21,30	★ 20,70	★ 21,60
<i>Sud</i>	★ 21,30	★ 21,60	★ 21,80	★ 21,60	★ 22,90
<i>Isole</i>	★ 20,90	★ 20,60	★ 20,30	★ 18,70	★ 18,80
<i>Italia</i>	★ 28,00	★ 27,80	★ 27,80	★ 26,80	★ 27,40

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